

**КОМПЮТЪРНА ПЛАТФОРМА ЗА ОЦЕНКА НА РЕНТГЕНОВИ
ИЗОБРАЖЕНИЯ: ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ ЗА ВАЛИДИРАНЕ НА АНТРОПОМОРФЕН
СОФТУЕРЕН МОДЕЛ НА МЛЕЧНА ЖЛЕЗА
Стойко Маринов, Иван Булиев, Живко Близнаков
Технически университет - Варна**

**SOFTWARE PLATFORM FOR EVALUATION OF X-RAY IMAGES:
APPLICATION FOR VALIDATION OF ANTHROPOMORPHIC SOFTWARE
BREAST MODEL
Stoyko Marinov, Ivan Buliev, Zhivko Bliznakov
Technical University of Varna**

Abstract: Aim of this study is to present a software tool designed to extract texture parameters from x-ray images. The tool is developed in the MATLAB environment and is dedicated to facilitate the research in x-ray imaging. A program called *BreastSimulator* is used to generate an anthropomorphic software model of an averaged in size breast. Further on, the computer model undergoes simulated mechanical compression to mimic the conditions during mammographic acquisition, and subsequently exported as STL file used for 3D printing. The physical model is printed with a stereolithographic 3D printer with resolution of 100 μm from Clear Resin. The model is then filled with animal fat and irradiated at GE Senographe digital mammography unit. On the other side, the software model is "irradiated" by a specialized program. The resulting x-ray images from both the simulated and the physical models are compared by their parameters, extracted with the help of the created software tool.

Keywords: x-ray images, texture analysis, software tools

I. Introduction

Anthropomorphic phantoms are important tools used as real tissue and organ substitutes for the purposes of diagnosis and analysis in medicine. The need for such alternatives is implied due to the limitations for the radiation exposure of the human body during x-ray diagnostic procedures, related to the amount of "harmless" radiation, at which there is no risk of causing a cancerous mutation of the irradiated human cells. The anthropomorphic phantoms offer possibilities to design, test and optimize new x-ray imaging modalities and see the effect of the radiation exposure on crucial parameters without causing harmful radiation effect to real human tissues. The anthropomorphic phantoms used in practice split in two main categories – (i) software phantoms, models of human tissues, organs, and parts of them, generated and processed entirely in a computer environment, and (ii) physical phantoms – material objects, representing real tissues and organs, consisting of different materials.

Physical substitutes are being used for longer time than the computer based counterpart, because of the computing power limitations of the technology few decades ago. Presently, these limitations are overcome by the use of clusters and cloud systems, which allow the accomplishment of very detailed and computationally heavy simulations in real time. Similarly, to the software models, the physical phantoms are used to substitute real human body parts. They are created, either using patient specific data or from computer based models. They are made of different materials, ranging from non-organic polymers and plastics to organic compounds, animal fat and others. These materials must have absorption characteristics close to these of the real tissue. Realistic physical three-dimensional phantoms with a tissue background are needed when investigations on the detectability of lesions, performance of image processing algorithms, reconstruction algorithms, optimization

of scanning parameters of new and existing imaging techniques, etc., are required. Manufacturing of such phantoms, however, is associated with several difficulties related to the current technology, suitable materials, manufacturing precision, size of the printed objects, etc. For these new phantoms, a proper evaluation and validation is necessary. Possible approach for that is to extract various parameters from x-ray images obtained from imaged phantoms and compare to the same parameters from clinical images. To facilitate this process, computerized tools are created and used.

Aim of this study is to create a tool, which facilitates the evaluation of such phantoms. The tool computes specific parameters such as standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis, as well as, performs fractal and spectrum analysis of user selected regions of interest (ROI). The developed tool was used in a specific task: to validate a complete model of an x-ray imaging chain, including modeling of a compressed breast, x-ray spectrum and x-ray image formation.

II. Materials and methods

The main purpose of the proposed tool is to provide means for specific processing of x-ray images and data extracting. The initial requirements for the functionality of have been the following:

- Access to images in DICOM format.
- Interaction with the images:
 - o Performing different computations over the ROIs: (a) Standard deviation; (b) Skewness; (c) Kurtosis; (d) Fractal analysis; (e) Spectrum analysis.

The software tool is created in MATLAB, using the GUIDE module, which allows for the creation of user interfaces as Windows applications. Figure 1 shows a snapshot of the GUI of the developed software tool. It consists of three main sub-windows for image importing, region selection and parameter calculation. For each ROI, the following parameters are calculated:

Standard Deviation is a measure that is used to quantify the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of data values. It is calculated by using eq. 1. A low standard deviation indicates that the data points tend to be close to the mean (also called the expected value) of the set, while a high standard deviation indicates that the data points are spread out over a wider range of values.

Figure 1. A screenshot from the graphical user interface.

Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real-valued random variable about its mean. The skewness value can be positive or negative, or even undefined:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

where σ is the standard deviation, x_i is each value in the data set, μ is the mean of all values in the data set and N is the number of values in the data set.

Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real-valued random variable about its mean. The skewness value can be positive or negative, or even undefined:

$$\gamma_1 = E\left[\left(\frac{X - \mu}{\sigma}\right)^3\right] = \frac{\mu_3}{\sigma^3} = \frac{E[(X - \mu)^3]}{(E[(X - \mu)^2])^{3/2}} = \frac{\kappa_3}{\kappa_2^{3/2}} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

where E is the expectation operator, μ_3 is the third central moment, σ is the standard deviation, μ is the mean of all values in the data set.

The *Kurtosis* measures the relative peakedness or flatness of a distribution. Kurtosis is calculated using eq. 3, where μ_4 is the fourth moment about the mean and σ is the standard deviation.

$$\text{Kurt}[X] = \frac{\mu_4}{\sigma^4} = \frac{E[(X - \mu)^4]}{(E[(X - \mu)^2])^2} \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Fractal analysis is assessing fractal characteristics of data. For planar images, the 'fractal dimension' is a characteristic of the inherent texture in the regions of the image. A lower fractal dimension corresponds to smoother texture and opposite. A mammography image of a fatty breast has a very coarse texture due to the good contrast between the connective tissue and the predominately fatty glandular tissue, while the mammography image of a dense breast appears to have smoother texture which corresponds to lower fractal dimension. The fractal dimension of a 2D image is calculated as:

$$A(\varepsilon) = \lambda \varepsilon^{2-D} \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

where $A(\varepsilon)$ is the area of the surface measured with a square of side ε , λ is a scaling constant and D is a constant characteristic of the surface (i.e. 'fractal dimension').

Power Law Spectral Analysis: The power spectrum of the ROIs was calculated by integrating the power spectrum density over concentric rings in the 2D frequency plane using the method in (Bliznakova 2010). If the image is marked as $f(a,b)$, then its power spectrum is computed from the discrete Fourier transform:

$$P(f) = |F(k,l)|^2 \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

$$F(k,l) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{a=0}^{M-1} \sum_{b=0}^{N-1} f(a,b) \exp\left[-2\pi i \left(\frac{ka}{M} + \frac{lb}{N}\right)\right], \quad k = 0,1,\dots,M-1 \quad l = 0,1,\dots,N-1 \quad \text{eq. 6}$$

where k and l are the spatial frequencies in the two directions, and $M \times N$ is the image size of $f(a,b)$.

The concentric rings represent an octave sectioning of the frequency plane. The ring width is half the width of the adjacent ring that covers higher frequency information, as the first octave corresponds to the highest frequency ring. The highest frequency is the Nyquist one. The total power spectrum per concentric ring is further transformed to $\log_2(\text{total power spectrum})$ and plotted versus the octave number. The plot is almost linear and the data are fitted to a line obtained after linear regression analysis. The slope of this line, m , is related to exponential parameter β as following:

$$m = \beta - 2 \quad \text{eq. 7}$$

III. Results

The software tool was applied to validate the accuracy of the *BreastSimulator* [1] to generate correctly x-ray mammography images. For this purpose, a small breast phantom was generated (Fig. 2a). Then, the breast model was compressed by using the same software application. The obtained compressed breast was subjected to processing, such as removing all tissues different than gland and skin (**Error! Reference source not found.**b). The model

Figure 2. Flowchart of the process for obtaining physical breast phantom (a) uncompressed breast model, (b) compressed breast model, (c) physical model.

was printed with a stereolithography printer and subsequently filled with animal fat (**Error! Reference source not found.c**).

A mammography image of the physical phantom was acquired with a GE Senographe SD digital mammography unit featuring a detector with a square pixel size of 0.1 mm and fully automatic exposure. The same geometry and exposure conditions were simulated with the *BreastSimulator*. Simulated and experimental images are visually compared in Figure 3. Further on, the calculated parameters for the quantitative comparison are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculated parameters for simulated and real images.

Figure 3. Visual comparison of mammographic images: a) real image b) simulated image.

Parameter	Real image	Simulated image
β	-2.43 ± 0.074	-2.51 ± 0.081
FD	2.14 ± 0.015	2.06 ± 0.001
Skewness	0.48 ± 0.335	0.47 ± 0.300
Kurtosis	1.76 ± 0.347	1.82 ± 0.260

IV. Discussion and Conclusions

The visual comparison between the images in Figure 3 shows a similar appearance of simulated and real mammography image. The objective quantitative evaluation demonstrates very good matching of the parameters for comparison. The graphical user interface is created in a simplistic, minimalistic and a user-friendly way, so that the whole process is visually simplified and easy to use.

This paper presents an in-house developed custom software tool, which facilitates the evaluation of x-ray images by extracting and calculating specific parameters, such as standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis, as well as, fractal and spectrum analysis. With the creation and use of such a specialized tool the time necessary for parameter extraction and comparison decreases significantly and the comparison procedure is facilitated.

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